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My Son is also My Daughter: Exploring the Deepest Sentiments, Feelings and Emotions of Parents

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Abstract

This study explored the phenomenon of the parents having gay sons. Specifically, it examined their lived experiences of having a gay son, their feelings and reactions upon knowing the sexual identity of their sons, and the insights that the conversational partners can share by parents with gay sons. This qualitative study used snowball sampling and was conducted using face-to-face interview with 20 parents. After careful data analysis using Colaizzi's method, findings reveal five major themes: living the life, lighter feelings, indifferent treatment, building bonds and heart's desire along with 20 core ideas and 270 significant statements. The CPs' experience having homosexual sons provided some implications: it is the primary responsibility of the conversational partners to serve as guide to their gay sons who encounter various experiences; ordinances and policies should be strictly implemented in school and in the society to protect gays from being bullied, and parents especially fathers should show acceptance to the sexuality of their children and recognize their role for the holistic development of their gay sons.

Keywords: *parent's sentiments, feelings, emotions, gay sons*

Introduction

"The truth shall set you free" (John 8:32). Parents expect their male children to behave like a red-blooded he-man and live up to their father's macho image. However, as time goes by, the parents' expectation turns into frustration because of the son's revelation that he is a girl trapped inside a boy's body. The Bible (Genesis 1:27) says that "so God created man in his image, in the image of God he created him; male and female He created them" (The Gideons International, 2013).

In Southeast Asia, specifically in Indonesia, gays are rejected as their neighbors. They believed that gay is forbidden by God and same-sex acts are criminalized by their law; therefore, gay people do not need to be protected and empowered (Manalastas et al., n.d). For them, being gay is a lifestyle that is avoidable if a person wishes to do so. Chamie and Mirkin (2011) said religion is vital in determining a person's societal role. Still, same-sex relationships are recognized in European countries such as Denmark, France, Iceland, and Norway.

In the Philippines, parents find it difficult to accept their sons' schooling experiences that are prone to bullying, discrimination, lack of access to LGBT-related information, and, in some cases, physical or sexual assault (Thoreson, 2017).

However, according to Human Rights Watch (2017), in Quezon City, an ordinance called the "Anti-Discrimination Bill" was passed to protect LGBT from harm and discrimination because those reported cases of abuse cause severe and lasting damage to gay students' right to education, that is protected under Philippine and international law.

The Department of Education adopted the anti-bullying policy through Republic Act 10627 and enforced DepEd Order no. 40 s. 2012, also known as "DepEd Child Protection Policy" and DepEd Order no. 55 series of 2013, otherwise known as "The Anti-Bullying Act of 2013". These policies ensure that students learn in a supportive, caring, and safe environment without fear of being bullied. Bullying happens when the individual or a group uses social media or power to hurt, either physically, emotionally, or verbally.

In the Southern part of Mindanao, specifically in the municipality of Alamada province of North Cotabato, there are a lot of gays that can be found everywhere. In some cases, parents do not admit that their sons are gay, which leads to frustration and depression. (Kranz, 2021). In addition, Neggle and Restoshy (2012) mentioned that some parents, however, understand their son's dilemma, and they become tolerant of the condition, which enriches their lives in so many ways and even provides opportunities.

The international and national realities of rejection, discrimination, and bullying experiences of gays, which are the results of quantitative research and likewise happening in the local settings, have motivated the researcher to conduct this qualitative study, delving into the most profound sentiments and feelings of parents with gay sons.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the world of parents having homosexual sons and how the phenomenon affects their lives. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of a conversational partner having a son who is gay?
2. How do the conversational partners describe their feelings and reactions upon knowing the sexual identity of their sons?
3. What are the insights that the conversational partners can share with parents of gay sons?

Methodology

This section presents the method used in this phenomenological study. Specifically, the following are included: research design, sampling design, the role of the researcher, conversational partners, data sources, data gathering procedure, instrumentation, face-to-face interview, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations.

Participants

The conversational partners for this qualitative study are 20 parents selected based on the following criteria. The CPs are ten mothers and ten fathers who have at least one gay son who is a high school student enrolled in Junior High School. The basic profile of the CPs, such as gender, age, educational attainment, type of work, and family income, is needed. Excluded in this research are those parents who live outside the Municipality of Alamada, their gay son is out of school youth, and those parents who did not admit that their son is gay.

Instruments

For a qualitative study, the researcher herself was the main instrument for data collection. The researcher observed, took down notes, and conducted the interview. Additionally, the researcher used an interview guide validated by panel members. This was the list of questions asked of the CPs during the interview. The order of the questions and the level and degree varied based on the type of interview conducted. The researcher asked questions about the experiences of the CPs to set the mood of the conversational partners, the challenges they encountered, how they coped with them, and their emotions during the first and second attempts. The researcher practiced extreme caution by using open-ended questions.

Procedure

To facilitate the study, the researcher first asked permission from the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study. Afterward, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the Schools Division Superintendent of Schools Division Office of Cotabato to administer the research study at Dado High School.

To get significant information for the study, the researcher oriented the conversational partners and reminded them about the importance of their responses. Afterward, the researcher conducted a face-to-face interview with the full cooperation of the selected CPs using data collection procedures such as observations, interviews, and personal data forms. First, the researcher presented the consent form to the participants and let them freely sign the agreement. Second, the guide questions were given to the participants a few minutes before the recorded interview so they could prepare their responses during the actual interview. Third, the CPs' consent for the interview was recorded and asked. Lastly, the researcher conducted the actual interview with some translations in the local language so that the CPs could express their point of view profoundly and with follow-up probe questions to explore their answers further.

Completing the transcription of the interviews, the researcher incorporated some notes from the participant's body language, tone of voice, expressions, and gestures following a particular question. The interview timing was based on the CPs' available time so as not to disturb their regular daily work. The CPs were interviewed at their most convenient time and place.

Therefore, the study presented the phenomenon since the CPs were free to express and share their personal experiences and beliefs without hindrances. To ensure that the transcriptions were correct, valid, and reliable, the researcher individually met with the CPs again so that they could verify the interview transcription. The researcher informed the participants that they could freely improve and delete some errors in the interview transcriptions and requested them to affix their signatures in the conforme section if they agreed.

Ethical Considerations

Observing ethical standards in research is essential. At the core, this helped shape the true aims of the study, such as knowledge, truth, and avoidance of error and promoted values essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. To ensure ethical research, this study followed and respected the principles of research ethics from the Belmont Report (2010). These principles respect a person's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, informed consent, confidentiality and data protection, integrity, and conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

The findings of the study are presented in Matrices generated from the thematic analysis.

Matrix 1 shows the conversational partners' profiles during the in-depth interview. There are 10 male and 10 female parents. Their ages are varied, ranging from 39 years old to 78 years old. In terms of their educational attainment, 2 are elementary undergraduates, 3 are elementary graduates, 4 are high school undergraduates, 9 are high school graduates, 1 is a college undergraduate, and 1 is a college graduate.

Regarding work or occupation, most are farmers; some are laborers, drivers, security guards, vendors, businesswomen, babysitters, and teachers, and some are homemakers. Regarding tribal affiliation, Ilonggos are the majority; some are Iranun, Ilocanos, and Cebuanos. Regarding Religion, most are Roman Catholics; some are affiliated with Islam, Baptist, and Iglesia Ni Cristo (Church of Christ).

The ideas expressed by the conversational partners were used to sort out the insights related to the salient results of their lived experiences, deepest sentiments, feelings, and emotions as parents having homosexual sons. To uphold confidentiality, code numbers were given to the respective conversational partners.

Matrix 1. Profile of the Conversational Partners

<i>Code Number</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Work</i>	<i>Tribe</i>	<i>Religion</i>
CP1-CB	40	Male	HS undergraduate	Laborer	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP2-AD	55	Male	ES undergraduate	Farmer	Iranun	Islam
CP3-ND	60	Male	College undergraduate	Driver	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP4-BM	39	Male	HS graduate	Security	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP5-DC	62	Male	ES graduate	Farmer	Ilonggo	Baptist
CP6-TM	66	Male	HS graduate	Farmer	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP7-SG	47	Male	HS undergraduate	Farmer	Ilocano	Catholic
CP8-SC	78	Male	ES graduate	Farmer	Ilonggo	Baptist
CP9-HB	44	Male	ES undergraduate	Driver	Cebuano	INC
CP10-RS	44	Male	HS graduate	Farmer	Cebuano	INC
CP11-NL	49	Female	HS graduate	Vendor	Ilocano	Catholic
CP12-SL	58	Female	HS graduate	Housewife	Cebuano	Catholic
CP13-IL	50	Female	HS graduate	Businesswoman	Cebuano	Catholic
CP14-RV	43	Female	College graduate	Teacher	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP15-ES	64	Female	HS undergraduate	Farmer	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP16-MM	60	Female	HS graduate	Housewife	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP17-EC	52	Female	HS graduate	Housewife	Ilonggo	Catholic
CP18-RN	39	Female	ES graduate	Housewife	Cebuano	Catholic
CP19-JB	39	Female	HS undergraduate	Businesswoman	Cebuano	Catholic
CP20-MS	39	Female	HS graduate	Baby sitter	Cebuano	INC

INC - Iglesia Ni Cristo

Matrix 2. Themes, Core Ideas, and Categorization of the Lived Experiences of Parents with Homosexual Son

<i>MAJOR THEMES</i>	<i>CORE IDEAS</i>	<i>CATEGORIZATION</i>
Living the Life	Feminine Actions	General
	Genetic and Environmental Influence	General
	Choices and Preferences	General
	Difficult to Request	Variant
	No Issues Encountered	Typical
	Good Qualities	General
	Mixed Feelings	Acceptance and Support
	Happy and Relieved	Typical
	Feeling Hurt and Worried	General
	Curious of the Reason	Variant
Indifferent Treatment	Not Accepted by Family and Other People	Variant
	Parents Ignoring Actions and Reactions	Typical
	Bullied or teased	Typical
	Inability to Communicate	Variant
	Hopelessness	Variant
Building Bonds	Parental Advice	Typical
	Fair Treatment	Typical
	Good Relationship and Open Communication	Typical
Heart's Desire	Entrusting to God	Variant
	Hope for the Best	Variant

Conclusion

Homosexuality is not appropriate in the sight of God or Allah if we are going to base on the Holy Bible or Quran. In a society wherein a gay exists, there is a notion that the gays are not fully accepted in the sight of some other persons that may result to bullying, unfair treatment, work deprivation or employment status, lack of support from some parents or family members.

Yet, as we live in this world, we should show love, support, respect and accept other person no matter what race, religion, sex do we have. Acceptance should always start at home. Some CPs still do not believe that their son is gay. They have high hopes and dreams for them but things fell down upon discovering of their homosexuality. Some scold them for being gay but some just ignore the reality.

Some CPs are also afraid of the consequences of their son being gay especially from being bullied and discriminated.

For this, we must always have faith in God. We may not understand all the things that happen to us but remember that everything happens for a reason. We need to trust God always. Also, we should treasure our family and friends, and all those people that we trust, for they will always be there for us. Importantly, we must always be strong in facing the adversities of life, including stress, because if we let stress defeat us, we might as well fail as a person.

This study is focused on the phenomenon of parents having gay sons. Twenty conversational partners which consist of ten mothers and ten fathers were asked to describe their feelings, reactions and insights having experienced dealing with their gay sons. The conversational partners (CPs) are limited to those parents from Alamada, Cotabato who have junior high school gay sons enrolled in a public high school in the school year 2021-2022.

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher highly recommends the following for possible courses of action which includes: Feelings and emotions of gay sons who are rejected by their families, and/or reasons of parents who find it difficult to accept that their son is a gay.

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